

Lack of Diversity in Hidradenitis Suppurativa Clinical Trials: A Cross-Sectional Analysis

Yanci A. Algarin, BS^{1,5*}, Anika Pulumati, BA^{2,5}, Dana Jaalouk, BS^{3,5}, Jiali Tan⁴ and Dr. Keyvan Nouri, MD, MBA⁵

¹Eastern Virginia Medical School, Norfolk, VA, USA

²University of Missouri-Kansas City School of Medicine, Kansas City, MO, USA

³Florida State University College of Medicine, Tallahassee, FL, USA

⁴Albany Medical College, Albany, NY, USA

⁵University of Miami Leonard M. Miller School of Medicine, Department of Dermatology and Cutaneous Surgery, Miami, FL, USA

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***Corresponding author:** Yanci A. Algarin, BS, Eastern Virginia Medical School, Norfolk, VA, USA

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To the Editor

Hidradenitis suppurativa (HS) is a chronic inflammatory skin condition, primarily caused by hair follicle occlusion that affects 0.3-4.1% of the global population¹. It is characterized by painful inflammatory nodules, abscesses, comedones, sinus tracts, and scarring, typically in intertriginous areas (Ex. axillae, inguinal regions, and gluteal folds). HS significantly impacts quality of life and psychosocial well-being, especially in patients with skin of color where scarring and hyperpigmentation are more apparent. Patients may also experience psychiatric comorbidities including depression and anxiety¹.

Disparities exist in HS prevalence, severity, diagnostic delays, and access to care, particularly affecting people of color². Data is limited on the racial and ethnic distribution of U.S HS clinical trials. Recent studies reveal underrepresentation of minority populations in HS clinical trials, potentially leading to insufficient data for informed treatment decisions, further exacerbating the existing healthcare disparities^{2,3}. Our study aims to assess the demographic composition of U.S. HS clinical trials compared to 2022 U.S Census data⁴.

In November 2023, authors searched the “<https://clinicaltrials.gov>” database using the following filters: Condition: Hidradenitis Suppurativa, Country: United States, Recruitment: Complete, Study Type: Interventional (Clinical Trial), Study Results: With Results. Ten of 26 identified clinical trials met our inclusion criteria, totaling

1,046 participants (Table 1). Of the participants, 68.2% (n = 713) identified as female and 31.8% (n = 333) identified as male. Moreover, 70.9% (n = 742) of participants identified as White, 5.4% (n = 56) as Asian, 20.5% (n = 214) as Black or AA, 0.96% (n = 10) as unknown or not reported, 0.57% (n = 6) as other, 0.96% (n = 10) as more than one race, 0.76% (n = 8) as American Indian or Alaska Native, and 0.0% (n = 0) as Native Hawaiian or Other Pacific Islander. Regarding ethnicity, 13.0% (n = 136) of participants identified as Hispanic or Latino, 85.9% (n = 899) as not Hispanic or Latino, 0.96% (n = 10) as unknown or not reported, and 0.10% (n = 1) as other. As compared to census data, White (71 vs 75.5%), Hispanic or Latino (13.0 vs 19.1%), Asian (5.4 vs 6.3%), American Indian or Alaska Native (0.76 vs 1.3%), and Native Hawaiian or Other Pacific Islander (0.0 vs 0.3%) groups were underrepresented, while Blacks or AA (20.5 vs 13.6%) were overrepresented.

Table 1: Demographic Makeup of United States Hidradenitis Suppurativa Clinical Trials

Sex representation of HS clinical trials (n= 1046)							
Male				Female			
32% (333)				68% (713)			
Racial representation of HS clinical trials (n= 1046)							
White	Black or African American	Asian	American Indian/ Alaska Native	Native Hawaiian/ Other Pacific Islander	More than one race	Other	Unknown
71% (742)	20% (214)	5% (56)	1% (8)	0% (0)	1% (10)	1% (6)	1% (10)
Ethnic representation of HS clinical trials (n= 1046)							
Hispanic or Latino		Not Hispanic or Latino		Other		Unknown	
13% (136)		86% (899)		0.1% (1)		1% (10)	

HS- Hidradenitis Suppurativa

Our study reveals underrepresentation of multiple minority groups in HS clinical trials compared to U.S. census data. Notably, AA are overrepresented, which differs from the typical underrepresentation^{2,3}. Factors potentially contributing to this overrepresentation include higher prevalence in AA populations, community engagement, and provider referrals. Ensuring appropriate demographic representation in clinical trials is imperative. The under- and over-representation of any group can bias research findings and hinder effective treatments for all. Clinicians must enhance trial diversity for a more comprehensive understanding of HS and improve care for all patients, thereby promoting health equity.

Keywords: Hidradenitis suppurativa; Skin of color; Clinical trials; Diversity

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Y.A.A. assisted with data collection and writing the manuscript. A.P. assisted with writing the manuscript. D.J. assisted with writing the manuscript. J.T. assisted with data collection and created (Table 1). K.N. assisted with writing the manuscript. All authors reviewed and approved the final manuscript

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